

Judul Artikel: “*User Acceptance and Behaviour Towards Tax Deduction Systems Adoption: An Integrated Technology Acceptance and Usage Model*”

Perspective Penulis:

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- I Gusti Made Karmawan
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Open Contributorship Evidence (CRediT taxonomy):

Nama	Peran Kontribusi	Keterangan Tambahan
I Gusti Ayu Tresza Dharmayani	Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Data Curation	Mengembangkan ide dan desain studi, menulis draf awal, mengolah data, menyebarkan kuesioner.
I Gusti Made Karmawan	Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Visualization	Mengumpulkan data lapangan dan melakukan analisis statistic, Literatur Review.
Levana Dhia Prawati	Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing	Melakukan pengumpulan data dan revisi akhir naskah.